

Effect of sheath rot on some yield components

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We studied the effect of sheath rot (ShR) on some yield components in an irrigated field of four plots planted to IR442-2-58 that was severely infected with *Sarocladium oryzae* Gams and Hawks.

Fifty plants per plot were randomly selected and evaluated for disease incidence. Individual tillers of each plant were rated using a 3-infection level scale (see figure). Healthy panicles made up 20.8% of the sample, 19.8% were in category 1, 13.5% in category 2, and 45.9% in category 3.

For further evaluation, 200 panicles from each disease severity category were harvested. Number of spikelets/panicle, percent filled spikelets/panicle, weight of filled grains/panicle, and 1,000-grain weight were recorded.

Percent filled spikelets/panicle was the yield component most affected by the disease, with only 2.7% recorded at scale 3 (see table). Number of spikelets/panicle and 1,000-grain weight were also significantly less for severely diseased panicles than for healthy ones. ShR significantly reduced yield per panicle and yield loss increased with increased severity.

Based on the measurements for yield/panicle within each disease severity category, and on the frequency of each category in the plots, the total yield loss associated with the disease was 52.8%. □

Severity rating scale (0 = healthy, normal panicle exertion, no discoloration or very few grains discolored; 1 = small brown lesions covering about 1/10 of leaf sheath, panicle exertion apparently normal, few grains discolored; 2 = larger lesions which tend to coalesce and may cover less than half the leaf sheath, about 65% or more panicle exertion, moderate grain discoloration; 3 = lesions have coalesced and may cover entire leaf sheath, no exertion to slight exertion of about 30% straight upward panicle, severe discoloration with whitish fungal growth).

Yield components of panicles with various sheath rot severity ratings.

Severity rating	1,000-grain wt (g)	Spikelets/panicle	Filled spikelets (%)	Relative yield (%)
0	24.9 a	164.2 a	95.0 a	100
1	24.3 a	178.5 a	90.7 a	88.3
2	22.3 b	171.4 a	59.8 b	62.4
3	14.8 c	144.5 b	2.7 c	1.2

^aHealthy and diseased panicles of IR442 selected in the field. Means in columns followed by different letters are significantly different at the 5% level.

Effect of herbicides on neck blast infection and rice yield

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Herbicides have been known to increase susceptibility of various plants to fungal and viral diseases. We studied the effect of herbicides commonly used in rice production on severity of neck blast (NBI) caused by *Pyricularia oryzae*, weed population, and rice yield in the field during

Effect of herbicides on NBI infection, weed population, and yield, Wangbal, Manipur, India.^a

Herbicide treatment	Application rate (kg ai/ha)	Weeds/m ²	Infection (%)	Yield (t/ha)
2,4-D	1.00	80	26.20 (30.64)	2.21
Fluchloralin	0.80	88	24.33 (29.46)	2.23
Pendimethalin	1.50	94	26.12 (30.67)	2.21
Oxyfluorfen	0.10	75	41.20 (39.90)	1.92
Thiobencarb	1.00	42	50.50 (45.09)	1.80
Butachlor	1.50	63	33.70 (35.47)	2.11
Untreated and nonweeded control		141	20.06 (26.60)	2.97
Weed-free check		0	16.95 (24.32)	3.60
CD (5%)			7.99	0.97

^aMean of three replications. Angular transformed values are in the parentheses.